

ABU RAYHON EVOLUTION OF NATURAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES

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Abstract: This article describes the life of Abu Rayhan Beruni, his contribution to the development of science by clarifying information about geography, geodesy, the shape and radius of the earth, geographical dimensions.

Key words: Abu Rayhan Beruni, geography, geodesy, cartography, mineralogy, globe, map.

Central Asia, including the land of Movorunnahr, is the land of many scientists and philosophers. The rich spiritual heritage left by our scholars is still studied and admired by scientists from all over the world. Abu Rayhan Beruni is a scientist distinguished by his high heritage in Central Asia. His real name was Abu Rayhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Beruni, born on September 4, 973 in the city of Khorezm. From a young age, Beruni was interested in astronomy, geodesy, geography and mineralogy. He made a great contribution to the development of these sciences. Beruni, his first teacher, was a great expert in astronomy and trigonometry and taught Beruni a lot of knowledge and experience. He started doing astronomy from the age of 17. Abu Rayhan Beruni is a scientist who contributed to the development of the science of geography through his high knowledge. He is the first among Central Asian scholars to say that the earth can rotate around the sun, to make a miniature model of the earth, i.e. a globe, to study the theory of land on the other side of the earth and the theory of continents moving closer to each other using the example of tree leaves. Beruniy gained his knowledge and experience by studying each field in depth. Based on the roundness of the earth and as a result of various

observations, Abu Rayhan Beruni gives the following opinion in the work "India": "We believe that there is land in the other quarter of the earth besides the northern quarter." This is Beruni's second opinion about the existence of a large land behind the ocean. In previous opinions, he emphasized that there is a land between two oceans and there is no possibility to go there. There are about 152 works of Abu Rayhan Beruni, 30 of which have reached us. 70 of these works are devoted to astronomy, 20 to mathematics and related sciences, 12 to geography and geodesy, 4 to mineralogy, 1 to physics, 1 to pharmacology, 15 to history and ethnography, 4 to philosophy, 18 to literature.

The rich scientific heritage left by Beruni has not yet been fully explored. His work dedicated to astronomy and geography, called "Determining the final limits of places for checking the distance between residential areas", which is called "Geodesy" in scientific literature, was completed in 1025.

In Beruni's works on geodesy, at the end of the 4 chapters of the book, he had several thoughts about measuring the magnitude of the earth's rotation. Since ancient times, people have been interested in knowing the shape and size of the earth, and different peoples have imagined the shape of the globe in different ways. Among Central Asian scholars, Abu Rayhan Beruni worked for 7 years at the academy named "House of Wisdom" established in Baghdad. Scientists of the Mamun Academy conducted studies in two groups. The scientists of the first group determined the size of the earth based on the degree measurement method in the Sadar desert west of Mosul, Iraq. Those in the second group calculated that the length of one degree of arc is equal to 111,815 km according to the results they measured, and those in the second group calculated that it was 1315 km less than the meter. And Abu Rayhan Beruni wants to study the degree measurement works by himself to determine the difference between the two results. Abu Rayhan Beruni had chosen the surroundings of Kasbiy. Unfortunately, due to the lack of assistants and funds to help Berunii, he could not do this work. Then Beruni expressed an opinion:

"To determine the size of the earth with a degree scale, a flat area of a certain latitude is needed, and here it is necessary to accurately measure up to several tens of kilometers. This work requires a lot of money and careful preparation. About this, Beruni said that the circumference of the earth can be determined as follows without wandering through the desert. For this purpose, by climbing a high mountain on the seashore or in a flat area, before sunrise or sunset, when half of the sun's halo is between the horizon, the angle of its descent is measured with a circular measuring instrument. All these measurement methods are explained and studied with diagrams and formulas.

In conclusion, the legacy of Abu Rayhan Beruni is widely researched as the most important scholarly source for each period. By measuring the distance of the Earth and its radius with greater accuracy compared to today, it gave a great impetus to the development of science. This information is still used today. Each of Beruni's works was highly appreciated and named after awards, higher educational institutions, and facilities. A state scholarship named after Beruni has been introduced for students who have achieved high results in their studies and scientific work. Statues of Beruni have been installed in Tashkent and Khorezm. Nowadays, our young people carry out research in various fields and continue the work of our great grandfather Abu Rayhan Beruni.

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